

THE IMPORTANCE OF USING FRACTALS IN CREATING PATTERN DECORATIONS

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ABSTRACT

In this article, we will discuss the importance of using fractals in creating pattern decorations and general information about fractals.

KEY WORDS: fractals, pattern, decorations, methodological tool, concepts, aspects, technologies

INTRODUCTION: According to a number of authors, in post-postmodern research practice “fractal analysis has proven to be a useful methodological tool in the humanities mathematics: in the economics of stock markets, sociology, urban studies, in the so-called mathematical history, synergetic concepts of culture, artmetry. In a certain sense the fractal concept began to claim a paradigm status in the science of the new centuries. In any case, the fractal as a paradigm concept initiates a “switch gestalt for the assembly of a new concept, for the recognition and interpretation of fractal structures in specific cognitive contexts, translating the concept of "Gestalt" into the concept "fractal structure".

MATERIALS AND DISCUSSION: A fractal is a geometric object, each of which is divided into parts similar to the original object. Fractals have infinity and are often self-similar and scalable. In most cases, fractals can be created through repeating patterns, recursive or iterative processes.

Unlike Euclidean geometry, the dimensions of fractals do not have to be integer values. In this branch of mathematics, points are zero-dimensional, lines are one-dimensional, surfaces are two-dimensional, and volumes are three-dimensional. In fractal dimension, it is a fractional quantity that represents how well a structure occupies the space it contains. The first fractals studied were the Cantor set, the Koch snowflake, and the Sierpinski triangle. Fractals can be

obtained geometrically or stochastically through recursive processes and can take on the characteristics of many different shapes found in nature.

Fractals are everywhere. There are many natural objects that are considered to be natural fractals based on their behavior or structure, but these are limited types of fractals that distinguish them from mathematical types of fractals created by recursive interactions. Examples of this are clouds and trees.

The word "fractal" comes from the Latin word *fractus*, which means "broken", "broken" or simply "broken" or "distorted" and is particularly suitable for objects with fractional dimensions. The term was coined by Benoit Mandelbrot in 1977 and appeared in his book *The Fractal Geometry of Nature*. The study of fractal objects is often referred to as fractal geometry. A fractal is a mathematical set that can enjoy self-similarity at any scale and whose dimensions are not integers, or if they are, not simple integers. Its self-similarity means that the fractal object does not depend on the observer itself, that is, if we take some kind of fractal, we can check that the drawing is the same as the first one at double magnification. If we zoom in by a factor of 1000, we check the same properties, so if we increase n , the plot is the same, so the part looks like the whole. [1.89] A collection or object is called a fractal if it becomes arbitrarily large as the scale of the measuring instrument decreases. There are many ordinary objects that are considered natural because of their structure or behavior, even though we do not recognize them. Clouds, mountains, shores, trees, and rivers are finite and therefore non-ideal natural fractals, unlike mathematical fractals, which are infinite and ideal. Fractal art is closely related to mathematics, especially geometry, because as its name suggests, it uses the concept of fractals. Fractals are based on the constant repetition of a self-connected geometric pattern, meaning that the part is equal to the whole. [2.65]

When constructing a Sierpinski triangle from an equilateral triangle, take its midpoint, create a new equilateral triangle and remove the center. Then do the same with each remaining triangle, and so on, so it's a fractal. Benoit Mandelbrot, who discovered the mathematical shapes known as fractals, has died of cancer at

the age of 85. Mandelbrot, a French and American citizen, developed fractals as a mathematical method to understand the infinite complexity of nature. [3.32]

To classify them from general to specific, we can divide them into two broad categories: deterministic fractals (which in turn can be algebraic or geometric) and non-deterministic fractals (also called stochastic fractals).

Linear fractals are built according to the variation of scales, which means that they are the same at all scales. [5.106] Nonlinear fractals, on the other hand, result from complex perturbations or, as the name suggest, to use the term in chaotic mathematics, nonlinear perturbations.

According to V.T. Shimko, in environmental design " the environment is perceived not so much as a system of visual terms, which gives consumers a certain visual image, how much as a special kind of emotional and aesthetic state (atmosphere or aura environmental object), where visual information about the material and physical "carriers" of this states are supplemented and corrected by the sensations of their purpose, stability existence and connection with the context. [4.89]

In our study, the dominant role belongs to the advertised clothing model; the accent can be either the model itself, or its individual parts, or elements of the background, revealing its meaning. The most diverse and unpredictable element of the WHC is background - that "backdrop" on which the correct reading of the meaning of an advertising message depends, its emotional content. So far, the semantics of this question in has not been sufficiently explored either in advertising or in costume design.

Pattern (Arabic - image, flower) - ornament (flower) consisting of stylized images of plants, birds, animals, etc. It is widely used in various objects (objects, weapons, cloth, furniture, books, etc.), architectural structures (both interior and exterior decorations), works of fine art (mainly, applied art), and in some nations, it is also used to decorate the human body (tattoo, intended for decoration). A pattern adorning the surface of an object reveals its structure and increases its artistic quality. The pattern is either composed of abstract shapes or stylized from specific

themes. [6.17] Depending on the raw material used, there are different styles and methods of pattern making: carving (wood, copper, stone, marble, etc.), painting (paper, fabric, wood, ceramic, etc.), embroidery using stitches (embroidery , goldsmithing, etc.), forging and casting (jewelry, coppersmithing, etc.), weaving (carpet making, textiles, etc.), carving (inlaying, latticework, etc.).

There is no specific information about the pattern's origin. The history of pattern is as old as the artistic culture of mankind. Archaeological materials show that the pattern has existed in all nations of the world since ancient times. In the Paleolithic and Neolithic periods, metal, pottery, dishes, and weapons were decorated with plant-like patterns in addition to simple geometric shapes. The pattern has developed differently in different countries and peoples under the influence of the geographical environment, flora and fauna, and culture. For example, in the motifs of the Northern countries, there are many images of juniper, cowherds, cattle horns, grape leaves and bunches of farmers, and flowers, pomegranates, almonds, and pepper. The artistic styles (baroque, gothic, classicism, etc.) that prevailed in Europe at different times had their influence on the pattern. During the renaissance, it gained a particularly high appeal. [1.28] From the end of the 19th century, the various currents that emerged during this period deliberately used the pattern sparingly, and even went so far as to completely abandon it.

Many purely mathematical and natural objects are not linear. In mathematics, self-similarity, sometimes called self-similarity, is the property of an object (called a self-similar object) in which a whole is exactly or approximately identical to an identical part, such as when the whole is identical. one or more in the form of its parts.

Add smaller and smaller details with successive iterations characterized by a fractal's perimeter tending to infinity. However, this curve does not conform to any time constraints of the circle surrounding the initial triangle. Clouds, mountains, circulatory systems, coastlines or snowflakes are natural fractals. This image is approximate because ideal objects have inherently limited properties such as infinite detail.

Previously, these models were used by us when considering the position of the theoretical physics about the torsion effect of art on the human bio field. In theoretical physics the concept of a torsion field or a torsion field (torsion - twisting) arises when perception of objects in the form of a set of twists or "small vortices" that have property of instant information transfer. This property is associated with their ability interactions with the physical and emotional structures of a person during perception works of art.

CONCLUSION: In conclusion, fractals can be used everywhere, and they are also very important in the art of patterning. Nowadays, in a time of rapid development of technologies, their use in the field of design opens the door to great opportunities.

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